

Moral Education Issues and Practical Approaches for Class Teachers in the Context of Cultivating Virtue and Fostering Talents

Yang Liu¹, Jinke Gao²

¹ Shandong Normal University

² The Middle School of Shenzhou

Email: 1083284540@qq.com (Corresponding author: Jinke Gao)

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Abstract

Cultivating students' moral character is the fundamental task of education in the new era. As the core implementer of moral education in schools, the effectiveness of class advisors is directly related to the achievement of educational goals. Currently, class advisors' moral education work faces multiple practical dilemmas: in terms of concept and practice, there are issues at different levels such as "personal professional limitations," "forms and contents of moral education," "synergistic force of moral education," and "evaluation of moral education." These dilemmas restrict the timeliness and effectiveness of moral education work. Therefore, this study proposes a systematic practical approach: first, reshaping concepts, promoting class advisors to start from their work cognition and elevate their own position; second, practical innovation, strengthening moral education practical experience; third, collaborative empowerment, making rational use of moral education resources and constructing a home-school co-education mechanism; fourth, changing perspectives, emphasizing diversified evaluation of students. Through the above paths, this article aims to promote the smooth and effective implementation of class advisors' moral education work, and effectively enhance the practical effectiveness of cultivating students' moral character.

Keywords: Cultivating Virtue and Fostering Talents; Moral Education for Class Teachers

1. Introduction

Cultivating students' moral character is the fundamental task of education in the new era. As the core implementer of moral education in schools, the effectiveness of class advisors is directly related to the achievement of educational goals. Currently, class advisors' moral education work faces multiple practical dilemmas: in terms of concept and practice, there are issues at different levels such as "personal professional limitations," "forms and contents of moral education," "synergistic force of moral education," and "evaluation of moral education." These dilemmas restrict the timeliness and effectiveness of moral education work. Therefore, this study proposes a systematic practical approach: first, reshaping concepts, promoting class advisors to start from their work cognition and elevate their own position; second, practical innovation, strengthening moral education practical experience; third, collaborative empowerment, making rational use of moral education resources and constructing a home-school co-education mechanism; fourth, changing perspectives, emphasizing diversified evaluation of students. Through the above paths, this article aims to promote the smooth and effective implementation of class advisors' moral education work, and effectively enhance the practical effectiveness of cultivating students' moral character.

2. Role orientation of the class teacher in moral education

2.1 Values guide

Within the scope of primary school head teachers' responsibilities, one of the core elements of moral education lies in the careful guidance and shaping of students' values. This guidance process encompasses multi-dimensional and multi-level content.

Firstly, for teachers themselves, they should set an example and be a behavioral role model for students, strictly demanding their own behavior and interpersonal attitudes. When educating students, teachers should pay attention to the process of guidance, and not just preach in a rigid way to instill values, but rather regard children as the main body of learning. In the current education system, many head teachers are accustomed to reinforcing memorization and recitation, or directly imposing their own values on students, in order to require students to internalize moral norms. This standardized operation mechanism ignores the emotional needs and cognitive patterns of individual students, resulting in cognitive internalization staying at the surface level of memory, inhibiting the cultivation of students' critical thinking, and causing a structural fracture between value identification and behavioral practice.

Secondly, fragmented education should be avoided. "Five educations" constitute a whole. If moral education is separated from the other four educations, it often becomes "isolated and unsupported" and cannot enhance its timeliness. Therefore, class advisors should integrate moral education with the other four educations to form a macro perspective on moral education, ensuring that the process of moral education for students encompasses the content of the other four educations. That is, while cultivating students' moral qualities, it is also necessary to instill humanistic literacy, knowledge literacy, aesthetic literacy, and labor skills(Ma,2024). In summary, fragmented education should be avoided, and one should not focus solely on one aspect while neglecting the others, so as to form an educational system that promotes and complements each other.

2.2 Emotional connector

Due to the special nature of their role, class advisors spend the most time with their students and understand each individual the best, making it easier for them to exert moral influence on their students. Therefore, class advisors should establish a good relationship with their students, pay attention to the growth and development of each student, listen patiently to their problems and troubles, provide timely care and guidance, and actively participate in students' lives and studies through individual conversations, class activities, and home visits, providing them with a good educational environment.

Firstly, it is essential to proactively identify the individual characteristics of each student and implement personalized education accordingly, rejecting the approach of treating all students with a uniform standard moral education model. On the one hand, personalized education demands that class teachers conduct systematic observations, in-depth exchanges, and scientific psychological assessments of students, comprehensively and accurately grasping the multi-dimensional personality traits of each student, such as interests, abilities, learning styles, and values. Based on this, they creatively design teaching activities, course content, and evaluation methods, ensuring that these elements closely align with the students' individual characteristics, thereby maximizing their learning potential and promoting the balanced development of their moral, intellectual, emotional, and social abilities. On the other hand, personalized education also emphasizes that educators should possess a high degree of flexibility and adaptability, seizing every educational opportunity and adjusting educational strategies in a timely manner according to the dynamic changes in students' growth process, ensuring that educational measures always match the current individual needs of students.

Secondly, class advisors should constantly adjust their psychological state and avoid treating students with a short temper due to their educational authority. Instead, they should communicate with students in a patient, listening, caring, and approachable manner, paying attention to students' emotional needs and providing emotional support. This communication approach helps break down barriers between teachers and students, making students more willing to share their feelings and confusion with teachers in an open mindset. This not only facilitates the construction of a

positive teacher-student relationship but also enables teachers to grasp students' thoughts and psychological dynamics more comprehensively. The core of education is to shape students' inner world, aiming to guide them in forming positive beliefs and values. Without the nourishment of emotions, this basic framework becomes difficult to maintain its vitality, which in turn affects whether students' moral education quality can be effectively improved (Ba, 2025).

2.3 Home-school coordinator

The class teacher serves as the primary channel connecting school and family, playing a significant role as a bridge for effective communication between these two parties. As for "collaborative education among family, school, and society", General Secretary Xi Jinping proposed at the National Education Conference that to run education well, it is necessary for families, schools, governments, and society to shoulder their own responsibilities. Among them, schools should bear the main responsibility, while paying attention to family education. The entire society should also create a good environment for the growth of the new generation of the times. Therefore, the role of the class teacher in coordinating between family and school cannot be ignored.

Firstly, the class teacher should respect differences, treat every student fairly, and maintain equality and respect towards all parents and students. The class teacher should deeply understand and fully respect the differences and uniqueness that exist among each student. At the same time, this respect should also be extended to all parents, in order to establish a home-school cooperation relationship based on mutual understanding and respect. There should be no favoritism or discrimination towards students and parents due to factors such as parental cooperation, social status, or educational background.

Secondly, class advisors should proactively establish a timely communication platform between home and school, engage in interactions with parents, and jointly discuss educational methods and activity content conducive to student growth, rather than simply conveying everything through students. Many moral education conflicts and contradictions between families and schools arise from poor communication, inefficient coordination, and monotonous communication methods. Therefore, it is of great practical significance for home and school to collaboratively build an efficient communication platform (Wang, 2023).

2.4 Growth Recorder

Firstly, it is important to clarify that one is not the leader of students' moral development, but rather a guide. Instead of positioning oneself as the center of moral education and arranging everything for students, one should respect the students' principal status and grant them more freedom and power to carry out and participate in moral education activities. At the same time, the class teacher needs to provide necessary guidance and support in this process, ensuring that the direction of moral education activities is correct and the content is appropriate, and providing timely feedback to help students summarize experience and reflect on their growth from practice. Such an educational approach not only promotes the comprehensive development of students but also enhances their sense of social responsibility and self-management ability, laying a solid foundation for becoming responsible and virtuous social citizens.

Secondly, it is necessary to create a growth portfolio, paying full attention to students' behaviors throughout their growth process, rather than solely relying on results to evaluate their moral development. In this process, class teachers should pay meticulous attention to students' inner development, such as emotional changes, the formation of values, the improvement of moral cognition, and the deepening of self-cognition. Although these factors are difficult to quantify, they are indispensable in measuring students' moral growth. Classroom interaction is an important observation window. Students' cooperative attitudes, listening habits, critical thinking, and respect for others in group discussions are all manifestations of their moral qualities. In addition, behavioral habits in daily life, such as honesty and trustworthiness, respect for others, and care for the environment, are also important bases for evaluating students' moral levels. Participation in community activities can further reveal students' growth in social responsibility, civic awareness, and leadership. In summary, the construction of a growth portfolio should be a multi-dimensional and comprehensive process. Class teachers should possess keen observation skills, profound insight, and meticulous recording abilities.

3. Limits of moral education work for class advisors

3.1 *The limits of personal professional competence*

The class teacher is the primary organizer and guide of moral education in the classroom. Their personal qualities, such as ideological, psychological, theoretical, and management qualities, largely determine the effectiveness of moral education in the classroom and influence the outcome of students' moral development. However, in reality, there are still many class teachers who, due to their lack of comprehensive qualities, conduct moral education activities that are more theoretical than practical.

Firstly, some class teachers fail to play a good role model in moral education. Due to the lack of educational training, occupational fatigue, personal values, and other factors, some class teachers inevitably exhibit negative behaviors when interacting with students. As key personnel in class management and educational teaching, if class teachers cannot play a good role model, it is likely to confuse students' moral concepts, making it difficult for them to form correct values and moral norms, affecting their moral development, and even leading to chaos within the class, causing students who have a strong desire to emulate their teachers to subtly imitate these inappropriate behaviors, resulting in collective behavior that is not standardized.

Secondly, due to the lack of effective communication skills in management or insufficient attention to students' needs, there is a lack of effective interaction between class teachers and students, making it impossible to deeply understand and solve the problems existing in students at this stage. This, in turn, affects the credibility of teachers and hinders the establishment of positive moral education relationships. Lastly, some primary school class teachers lack theoretical knowledge in moral education. On the one hand, they lack systematic and in-depth learning of moral education theories, making their judgments on students' moral issues inaccurate and unable to theoretically explain and guide students' behavior. On the other hand, they have insufficient understanding of children's psychological development patterns, often neglecting students' psychological needs and developmental stage characteristics in the process of moral education, and thus unable to fully mobilize students' inherent moral consciousness and emotional experience.

3.2 *The limits of moral education about forms and content*

The content and form of moral education are both extremely important. They complement each other and jointly determine the effectiveness of moral education. However, in real-life moral education work, the themes of most class meetings are usually determined and issued by the school, then communicated to the class teacher, who then conducts the moral education themed class meeting accordingly. The themes set by the school are almost all aimed at meeting the requirements of superiors. Most of the content or themes of moral education still remain at the most basic level, such as ideological and political education, student codes or disciplines, without paying enough attention to students' psychological quality, frustration education, life education, online moral education, and legal education. Ultimately, this leads to students having poor stress resistance and even a series of psychological problems, which can ultimately result in bitter consequences and even the cost of life. Nowadays, research on many problematic students with internet addiction, school weariness, and selfish behavior has found that it is often due to issues with primary school students' values, outlook on life, and consumption attitudes(Wang,2020). Even if some class teachers can appropriately adjust the themes of moral education, there may still be situations where moral education activities are conducted in a dominant manner without fully considering the actual needs of students for moral education content.

The form of moral education plays a crucial role in students' understanding and internalization of its content. If the form is too single and rigid, it can make students feel bored and uninterested, creating a sense of distance from the moral education content. In real-life moral education, some class teachers still mainly rely on oral indoctrination of moral concepts and knowledge, neglecting actual interaction and participation with students, and seldom guiding students to apply these theoretical knowledge to real life. This one-way indoctrination of moral education keeps students' understanding of the moral education goals at the theoretical level, making it difficult to stimulate students' moral emotions and even more impossible to promote the development of students' moral behavior.

3.3 The limits of moral education synergy

Parents are the first teachers of their children, and the family is the first school for them. Therefore, the influence of the family on children is no less than that of the school. However, in the traditional model of joint education between home and school, the school often occupies a dominant position in most cases, while the role played by the family tends to be marginal.

For schools, an important reason lies in the misconception of some head teachers. Some head teachers believe that relying solely on themselves to conduct moral education is sufficient for students, and that parents' educational backgrounds and levels vary greatly. If many parents come to offer opinions on their work, it will inadvertently threaten their "teacher authority". Therefore, they develop a sense of distrust towards parents and are unwilling to spend time and energy communicating and working together on moral education. For parents, influenced by traditional concepts, on the one hand, many parents still unconsciously place themselves in a subordinate position to teachers, believing that teachers, especially head teachers, are the absolute authority in moral education and the most professional personnel. They feel that they have no right to interfere with their daily management and educational work, so many parents unconsciously shift the responsibility of moral education to schools, thinking that schools are the main place for moral education. However, as the primary educational responsible party and taxpayers of students, parents have the right to participate in school education(Liu,2022)6. On the other hand, in the new era, the family factors that affect the implementation of moral education are mainly manifested as differences between school and family educational goals. Under the promotion of quality education, primary schools begin to focus on cultivating students' thinking ability, mental health quality, behavioral norms, moral literacy, etc. However, some parents still place their focus and standards for student development on academic performance, ignoring the comprehensive attention to children's physical and mental health as well as ideological conduct, leading to significant deviations in the goals of school and family education, and thus affecting home-school cooperative education(Wu,2023). If moral education can only rely on internal guidance and lacks the cooperation of family education, it will fail to achieve its desired effect and value.

3.4 The limits of moral education evaluation

Moral education evaluation involves qualitative or quantitative assessment and analysis of an individual's performance in terms of character, morality, and values. Its purpose is to measure students' moral qualities, character cultivation, and sense of social responsibility, and to guide schools and teachers in carrying out moral education work through the evaluation results. However, there are many issues with current moral education evaluation.

Firstly, the evaluation method is overly quantitative. Under the heavy pressure of China's current educational system, which emphasizes further education and exam-oriented education, a teacher evaluation system has been formed that is based on exam scores, job performance based on scores, and promotion based on students' academic achievements. Even though this evaluation can provide clear indicators and standards, making the evaluation results more transparent and comparable, and improving the efficiency of educational management, mechanical quantitative evaluation is still insufficient to evaluate students' true moral status, and it is filled with "dehumanized" judgments towards teachers and students. True morality is the integration of knowledge and action, the unity of "conformity to responsibility" and "out of responsibility". That is to say, whether the evaluation subject possesses true morality depends not only on whether their behavior conforms to morality, but also on whether the motivation behind their behavior is driven by morality(Jiang,2023). This means that quantitative assessment is merely a means, with the purpose of educating and cultivating people, and if this purpose is not achieved, then moral education evaluation loses its significance.

Secondly, the evaluation subject is singular. For a long time, due to the influence of traditional concepts moral education evaluation has often been dominated by authoritative subjects such as educational administrative departments, schools, and teachers. That is to say, it is usually they who evaluate students based on their own observations and evaluation criteria, while students and parents often passively accept the evaluation results and lack

participation in moral education evaluation. Under such an evaluation system, there is a lack of communication and interaction among teachers, students, parents, and other subjects, making it difficult to form an evaluation model of joint participation and mutual support. Consequently, students and parents are dissatisfied with the evaluation results, affecting their confidence in the school's moral education work.

In summary, to fulfill the educational function of moral education evaluation, positive changes must be made in the above-mentioned aspects.

4. Reasons for the existence of limitations in moral education by class advisors

4.1 Outdated moral education philosophy and low self-perception

Ideas influence behavior. Having a correct moral education concept that aligns with the times is the starting and ending point for class advisors in carrying out various moral education tasks. General Secretary Xi Jinping once said, "To be a good teacher in the information age, one should know far more than what they teach to their students. They should not only possess professional teaching knowledge, but also have extensive general knowledge and a broad mindset and vision. A good teacher should possess wisdom in learning, social interaction, living, and educating people. They should not only teach people how to fish, but also teach them how to fish, and be able to help and guide students in all aspects."(Xi,2014) In today's era of information explosion and rapid changes in the world, some class advisors lag in updating, learning, and applying moral education concepts, resulting in a series of moral education activities that are disconnected from the reality of students and fail to achieve the desired moral education effects. At the same time, they may rely too much on traditional moral education methods, ignoring the diversification, emotionalization, and practicality advocated by modern moral education concepts, leading to many problems.

Some class advisors have a biased understanding of their role, viewing moral education as an incidental task rather than the core of their educational responsibilities, and thus lacking the necessary attention and dedication to moral education. This misconception not only undermines the class advisors' leading role in moral education but also leads to moral education becoming a mere formality, unable to truly penetrate into daily teaching and management. Furthermore, due to the significant social pressure currently faced, the work environment of class advisors is filled with supervision and pressure from parents, schools, and other social groups. When issues arise, class advisors often face reports from parents or criticism from public opinion, which makes many of them tend to adopt a more conservative management approach in their work. Their primary goal is to "avoid accidents," thus preferring to adopt a series of seemingly safe but inappropriate management measures. In this situation, class advisors often tend to simplify moral education into the mechanical enforcement of discipline, rather than guiding students to form sound values and behavioral habits through moral education, ultimately preventing moral education from playing its due role.

4.2 Weak innovation concept, with emphasis on moral education theory

The lagging moral education concept of class advisors is influenced by both subjective and objective factors. Subjectively, some class advisors are influenced by the traditional "score-first" mindset, placing more emphasis on students' academic performance in educational practice. Their understanding of moral education remains at the previous level, neglecting the core position of moral education and the importance of innovation in moral education work. This tendency to prioritize intellectual education leads to moral education work being superficial, lacking substantial progress and deep moral guidance. As a result, students lag in the cultivation of values, moral cognition, and behavioral habits, failing to keep pace with their intellectual development. Over time, although students may achieve excellent academic results, they may appear confused and immature when facing moral judgments, social responsibilities, and interpersonal relationships in real life. Therefore, it can be said that updating moral education concepts is not only an enhancement of class advisors' educational capabilities but also a necessary guarantee for students' comprehensive development. Objectively, class advisors have to deal with many daily class chores, various tasks assigned by the school outside of teaching, as well as communication and exchanges with leaders and parents, which can easily lead to teacher burnout. This makes them unwilling to spend extra time and energy on systematic moral education training, learning new moral education theoretical knowledge and educational concepts, resulting in a

disconnect between moral education concepts and the requirements of the times, affecting their attitude towards implementing moral education and the improvement of their own moral education implementation abilities.

Moral education, when applied to students, should be implemented in four aspects: knowledge, attitude, intention, and behavior. However, at the current stage, many class advisors still focus primarily on the theoretical preaching of moral education, neglecting the emotional and behavioral aspects. Overall, relying excessively on traditional theoretical moral education will make it difficult for students to establish solid moral cognition and behavioral patterns in today's diverse and complex society, which is not conducive to comprehensively improving students' moral education literacy.

4.3 Insufficient awareness of resource utilization and inadequate communication between home and school

The new curriculum standards mandate that moral education content keep pace with the times and align more closely with students' family environments and socialization development characteristics. However, current school moral education primarily emphasizes internal discipline and norms, with materials mainly sourced from school life, neglecting students' interactions and experiences in authentic family or social environments. Additionally, educational resources can be divided into explicit and implicit ones based on their role and mode of presentation. Therefore, as important implementers of moral education work, in addition to paying attention to and applying explicit resources, class teachers should also actively explore and extract implicit moral education elements that permeate students' daily behaviors and teachers' regular teaching practices, starting from multiple dimensions such as the construction of campus culture, shaping of class environments, and improvement of teachers' professional ethics(Yao,2024).

Inadequate communication between home and school is also a significant factor that contributes to the poor effectiveness of moral education. In the process of educating children, home and school are two crucial links. If there are obstacles or deficiencies in communication between home and school, both parties will be unable to fully understand the child's performance and needs in both settings. Consequently, it becomes difficult to form a consistent educational philosophy and effective educational strategies, preventing family education and school education from combining their efforts in moral education. This may even lead to negative effects that cancel each other out. Classroom moral education in the new era requires the implementation of "holistic education," which means educating students in an all-round, inclusive, and comprehensive manner(Yang,2022). Therefore, strengthening communication between home and school and ensuring close cooperation and effective interaction between both parties in the process of educating children is a crucial guarantee for enhancing the effectiveness of moral education and promoting the comprehensive development of children.

4.4 The evaluation perspective is overly focused on quick success and instant benefits, with a profound influence from exam-oriented education

Fundamentally speaking, the evaluation of students' moral education is neither an end nor a proof, but a means to promote students' pursuit of goodness and beauty and self-improvement. Individual moral qualities and values are gradually formed through continuous practice, reflection, and correction. Therefore, moral education needs to adopt a gradual approach, guiding individuals step by step towards a higher moral realm. However, currently, most schools' moral education activities are merely superficial, and moral education evaluations are mostly aimed at enhancing the external image of the school or coping with inspections from superiors. Schools and teachers regard moral education evaluations as a means to improve school rankings. The primary school stage is a critical period for moral cultivation. If students are always treated with such utilitarian evaluations, it will not only be unhelpful for school moral education work but also detrimental to students' moral development, deviating from the educational philosophy of cultivating students' moral character.

The rigidity of moral education evaluation is largely influenced by the exam-oriented education system. Firstly, against the backdrop of fierce competition for higher education, exam scores and grades have become the primary criteria for measuring the performance of students and teachers. However, true morality involves the integration of knowledge and action, while quantitative assessments often only measure students' external behaviors, failing to delve

into the motivations and qualities behind their actions. Secondly, influenced by traditional exam-oriented education concepts, moral education evaluation has long been dominated by authoritative entities such as educational administrative departments, schools, and teachers, while students and parents are in a passive position of accepting evaluation results. This single-entity evaluation model lacks communication and interaction among multiple parties, making it difficult to form a collaborative and mutually supportive assessment approach. This leads to dissatisfaction among students and parents with the evaluation results, which in turn affects their confidence and support for school moral education work. Lastly, moral education evaluation involves students' performance in terms of morality, ethical behavior, and social responsibility, which are relatively difficult to directly quantify and objectify. Exam-oriented education makes class teachers focus more on improving students' grades and neglect the process of students' moral development, devoting most of their energy to students' learning and paying little attention to or ignoring those evaluation aspects that are difficult to quantify. Therefore, fixed standards are often adopted in the evaluation process, leading to relatively static evaluation results.

5. Method

5.1 *Deepen work cognition and elevate personal standing*

Cognition determines behavior. Moral education is the soul of education and an important task of basic education. Class advisors should recognize that they are not only transmitters of knowledge but also shapers of students' moral behavior, playing a crucial role in the formation of students' outlook on life, values, and worldview. Therefore, in moral education work, class advisors should actively update their concepts and pay attention to the moral needs of contemporary society. With the development of the times, the moral challenges faced by students are increasingly complex. Traditional preachy and indoctrination-style moral education methods are no longer sufficient to address these challenges. It is necessary to introduce modern moral education concepts and integrate more experiential, interactive, and life-oriented moral education models to help students internalize moral concepts in real-life situations.

Moral education is by no means merely an incidental task or an additional aspect of education. It constitutes a crucial core component of educational responsibilities. It encompasses not only the imparting of moral knowledge or the training of skills, but also the nurturing and guidance of students' inner worlds. Its aim is to cultivate well-rounded socialist builders and successors who possess noble moral sentiments, good behavioral habits, and correct value orientations. Therefore, placing moral education at the core of educational work is an educational philosophy that every educator, especially class teachers, must deeply understand and resolutely practice. On this basis, class teachers should face the practical issues of moral education head-on, approach moral education with a positive and open mindset, pay attention to the moral education situation of every student, teach students according to their aptitudes, constantly reflect on their learning, and accumulate moral education experience.

5.2 *Update moral education concepts and strengthen practical experience*

Society is constantly developing and changing, with new technologies, cultures, and social concepts emerging one after another, posing higher requirements for students' all-round development. Firstly, the homeroom teacher should abandon the traditional moral education concept that puts scores first. It should be clear that in addition to academic performance, students' comprehensive qualities are also important, such as teamwork ability, innovation ability, social skills, etc., which should be paid attention to in moral education. Secondly, to change the traditional preaching and moral education model, it is necessary to establish a good teacher-student relationship with students, listen to their voices, understand their confusion and needs, help students solve psychological problems through active emotional communication and psychological counseling, and enhance their confidence and sense of responsibility.

Moral education practice activities are an important extension and supplement of moral education, and an effective path to cultivate students' sense of social responsibility and enrich practical experience(Wang,2024). To pay attention to the development of students' knowledge, will, and behavior in all aspects, it is necessary to explore new ways of moral education. The new approach to moral education can be organized from two aspects: new forms of classroom practical activities and classroom cultural construction. In class activities, participating in class activities

requires students to fulfill certain roles and responsibilities, which helps cultivate their sense of responsibility and self-discipline. At the same time, the experience of joint participation and effort can also stimulate students' sense of identification with the class collective. Therefore, the homeroom teacher should fully utilize the role of activities in students' moral education. For class culture, it can be divided into two aspects: institutional culture and spiritual culture. There are various types of institutional culture, such as elementary school rules, class regulations, class cadre systems, etc. It is an important measure to evaluate students' character and behavior, and students can consciously regulate their words and actions under its constraints. When formulating the class system, teachers should integrate moral education elements into it, and also brainstorm, mobilize the whole class to participate in the formulation, fully exert students' subjectivity, reach a consensus on moral concepts, and enhance their sense of responsibility and self-restraint. For spiritual culture, it can create a good classroom atmosphere, and students will naturally develop positive and proactive moral behavior in such an environment and atmosphere.

5.3 Reasonably utilize resources and collaborate with families and schools for joint education

Moral education resources are essential material and spiritual conditions for the existence and development of moral education. They are the source and foundation for doing a good job in moral education. Reasonable allocation and integration of moral education resources can improve the effectiveness of moral education. The moral education resources in schools, no matter how authoritative, are limited. Therefore, class teachers should actively utilize various resources such as family, community, and technology to carry out moral education work. Firstly, the homeroom teacher can actively utilize internal resources of the school, such as psychological counselors, moral education experts, etc., to establish a team cooperation mechanism. By collaborating with these professionals and regularly educating and guiding students, class teachers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of students' psychological conditions and behavioral characteristics, and provide more targeted moral education guidance. Secondly, the rich life experiences of parents of students are also excellent moral education resources that can be utilized. Parents have different professions, but regardless of their profession, they can actively provide opportunities for parents to participate in the classroom. Finally, community resources can be utilized to carry out moral education work. For example, cooperative relationships can be established with social organizations, volunteer groups, etc., to provide students with various forms of moral education activities and services such as volunteer activities, social practices, lectures, etc., thereby broadening students' social horizons, cultivating their sense of social responsibility and teamwork ability.

Co education between home and school is also an important approach to moral education for students in the context of the new era. Based on the collaboration between families, schools, and communities, moral education can promote cooperation among teachers, parents, and community educators. By applying this moral education model, multiple educational resources can be integrated with students as the center, thereby exerting a comprehensive influence on their moral development(Zhu,2024). Firstly, the homeroom teacher should collaborate with other subject teachers to carry out interdisciplinary learning, jointly develop moral education resources in textbooks, and achieve consistency and continuity in the impact of moral education. Secondly, the homeroom teacher can carry out interactive activities between home and school to promote effective communication with parents. Regular parent teacher meetings, home visits, and other activities can help class teachers understand students' family environment, which can provide reasonable explanations for students' moral behaviors and enable targeted measures to be taken. Finally, the homeroom teacher can enhance interaction with students through modern technological means such as online platforms, social media, etc.

In short, by making reasonable use of these resources, class teachers can establish a diversified and comprehensive moral education system, collaborate with schools, families, and communities, and provide students with more comprehensive and personalized moral education support.

5.4 Establishing a correct evaluation perspective and valuing diverse evaluations

With the development of society and the transition from exam oriented education to quality education, new problems have emerged in school moral education work, and traditional moral education evaluation methods and

perspectives have gradually become bottlenecks for the deepening development of quality education. Therefore, it is imperative to reform the evaluation of students' ideological and moral character. If class teachers want to optimize the moral education evaluation system, how to establish a correct evaluation concept, and fully play the important role of moral education evaluation.

Firstly, it is important to emphasize the combination of quantity and quality in evaluation. Undoubtedly, quantitative moral education evaluation methods can be evaluated, operated, and utilized, providing students with a clear indicator for reference. However, there are still some unreasonable aspects in their specific implementation and application of results, such as often only evaluating students' simple behaviors and outcomes based on some rigid indicators, which cannot fully reflect the complexity and diversity of students' moral development. Therefore, quantitative evaluation should be combined with qualitative evaluation, and we should pay more attention to qualitative evaluation. Qualitative evaluation can start from the aspects of grade evaluation, comment evaluation, and refined evaluation, dividing students into different grades or levels. Common levels can include excellent, good, qualified, in need of improvement, etc. They can also be classified using letter levels, symbol levels, or symbols that children enjoy. Therefore, the qualitative evaluation of moral education is an important way to assess students' morality. The class teacher should fully utilize and balance the advantages of both evaluations, and jointly promote the development of students' morality towards goodness.

Secondly, diversified evaluation subjects should be adopted. Schools and homeroom teachers should achieve 'delegation of power', which means handing over the right to evaluate students to multiple stakeholders such as students themselves, classmates, and parents. Because this can provide evaluation information from different levels and perspectives, more accurately assessing the moral education level of the evaluated person, thereby enhancing the validity of the evaluation. One of the essential aspects of moral education is the process in which students construct their own moral character under the guidance of teachers. The mutual evaluation among classmates can enable others to observe and evaluate each other's behavior more objectively as bystanders. For parents, they have a better understanding of their children's family environment and upbringing background, which can provide deeper insights and evaluations of student behavior that schools do not have, promote communication and cooperation between schools and families, and form a closed loop of education.

6. Discussion

In summary, under the background of cultivating moral character, class teachers should attach importance to improving their own qualities, deepening their work cognition, updating their moral education concepts, coordinating various subjects such as family, school, and society, fully utilizing and exploring effective moral education resources, actively carrying out various moral education practice activities suitable for children's physical and mental characteristics, and timely, fairly, and actively evaluating the development of children's moral education, promoting every student to achieve their own development in all aspects under the orderly development of class teacher's moral education work, and becoming an excellent builder and successor of the socialist cause. Ten years to grow trees, a hundred years to cultivate people. "The moral education work of the homeroom teacher is a protracted battle; Sneaking into the night with the wind, moistening everything silently." "The moral education work of the homeroom teacher is another" silent "long-term battle. I believe that with the concerted efforts of the class teachers, the moral education work of the school will develop smoothly, effectively and orderly, and win this' silent and protracted battle smoothly.

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